

DOI: 10.15276/ETR.06.2020.8
 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4564580
 UDC: 35(477):004.738.5
 JEL: E23

INTRODUCING E-GOVERNANCE BOTH IN UKRAINE AND IN THE WORLD

ВПРОВАДЖЕННЯ ЕЛЕКТРОННОГО УРЯДУВАННЯ В УКРАЇНІ І В СВІТІ

Svitlana S. Sviridova, PhD in Economics, Associate Professor
 Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine
 ORCID: 0000-0002-4299-7422
 Email: Sviridov3aS@gmail.com

Alisa O. Bondarenko
 Odessa National Polytechnic University, Odessa, Ukraine

Received 20.12.2020

Свірідова С.С., Бондаренко А.О. Впровадження електронного урядування в Україні і в світі. Оглядова стаття.

В статті досліджено основні нормативно-правові засади розвитку електронного урядування в Україні та за кордоном. Проаналізовано сутність, особливості та переваги функціонування технологій електронного урядування. Визначено сучасний стан електронного урядування в Україні в порівнянні зі станом його впровадження в країнах Європи та інших країн, відповідність законодавства України завданням розвитку електронного урядування. Встановлено, що на світовій арені електронне урядування розуміється як фактор зростання конкурентоспроможності держави. Інструменти електронного урядування для нашої держави є відносно новими, Україна значно відстає за темпами впровадження електронного урядування (82 місце серед 193 країн за результатами комплексного оцінювання розвитку E-Government In Support of Sustainable Development у 2018 році).

Систематизовано основні характеристики світових моделей електронного урядування в порівнянні з Україною.

Ключові слова: інформаційне суспільство, електронне урядування, інформаційно-комунікаційні технології, електронні послуги, адміністративні послуги.

Sviridova S.S., Bondarenko A.O. Introducing E-Governance both in Ukraine and in the World. Review article.

The article examines the basic legal framework for the development of e-Governance both in Ukraine and abroad. The essence, features and advantages of functioning of e-government technologies are analyzed. The current condition of e-Governance in Ukraine in comparison with the status of its implementation in European countries, the compliance of Ukrainian legislation with the e-governance objectives is determined. It is established that on the global stage e-Governance is understood as a factor in increasing a state's competitiveness. E-Governance implements for our country are relatively new, so Ukraine lags far behind in the pace of e-Governance implementation (82d place among 193 countries in the comprehensive assessment of E-Government In Support of Sustainable Development in 2018).

The main characteristics of the world models of e-Governance in comparison with Ukraine are systematized.

Keywords: information society, e-Governance, information and communication technologies, electronic services, administrative services

In modern conditions of social development, there is a great awareness of the need to transform the entire system of public administration. This is primarily due to the transition from the information society to the knowledge society, which radically changes all the communications in society and places new demands on the services quality provided by civil servants. E-Governance is a modernization process of the public administration system, which includes providing quality services both for citizens and businesses, and the latest communication channels establishment between government and civil society, the entire civil service reengineering.

Analysis of recent researches and publications

Various scientists are engaged in the problems of introducing e-Governance in Ukraine, analysis of applying the electronic technologies in the field of public administration, researches of the created base of e-Governance in the European countries, among them it is necessary to allocate: A. Semenchenko, O. Holubotskyi, S. Chukut, I. Klymenko, V. Furashev, D. Lande, D. Dubova, S. Dziuba, A. Semenchenko, S. Clift and M. Bones.

The aim of the article is to get acquainted with the basic principles and best practices of e-Governance both in European countries and in Ukraine.

The main part

The science of public administration is in constant development and the search for more effective and adequate to modern conditions and needs methods, principles and implements of public administration. Both the theory and methodology of e-Governance may be replaced by more modern ones in a few years. Nowadays, such approaches to public administration as the new institutional and synergetic ones compete with them. At the same time, different public administration strategies can be used.

In Ukraine, e-Governance is developing through the projects implementation and cooperation of the all

government agencies and local governments with the international partners' support.

Experts in the field of information technologies believe that G-governance is the key to reform in Ukraine, because it is impossible to achieve high rates of transformation without introducing digital technologies in every area, and that these processes understanding demonstrates most state and local authorities.

At this stage, e-services are the most common area in the field of e-Governance, because they apply to every citizen of the country.

At the end of 2018, the main task in Ukraine was introducing more than 100 electronic services, the list of which included the highest priority by businesses and citizens. To date, 118 electronic services have been created, among which there are socially important ones – childbirth assistance registration, business registration services, services in the agricultural and construction fields [8].

In 2019, important sets of electronic services for drivers and carriers were launched, which are available in their electronic offices. These services are already in high demand. Also in Ukraine, the first fully automatic service has appeared, the decision on which is not made by an official. Namely – about the beginning of construction works for the CC1 class. [10]

In Ukraine, the preparatory stage for introducing the electronic document management in the executive authorities based on electronic digital signature has been completed, namely:

- a set of uniform formats and protocols of electronic document management and electronic digital signature has been developed, the formation of which took place with the broad participation of business representatives, scientists and government agencies specialists.
- the electronic exchange order of official documents has officially been defined, which is a prerequisite for the disparate information systems integration, that will ensure their compatibility and effective interaction.

Despite the positive dynamics of the electronic information resources development in Ukraine, unresolved problems remain the departmental approach to their creation, significant duplication of information, lack of common standards and resources incompatibility, difficult access etc. As a result, today there is no possibility to provide integrated public services, including administrative, electronic means.

In order to understand the process of introducing e-Governance, as well as the mechanism for its implementation, we should pay attention to the most common models of G-governance in the world.

There are different approaches to defining the e-Governance model. The most common and simple (classic) of them describes the links between the main subjects of e-Governance and includes such components as:

- "Government to Government" (G2G – "government to government") – electronic interaction between authorities, primarily in order

to provide electronic services by some authorities to others;

- "Government to business" (G2B – "government to business") – electronic interaction of government agencies with business entities in order to provide the latter with administrative and other services, business participation in forming and implementing the public policy, in public procurement, etc.;
- "Government to Citizens" (G2C – "government to citizens") – the authorities electronic interaction with citizens in order to provide services to citizens, the citizens' participation in the formation of public policy and the election process, evaluating and monitoring government activities, etc. Access to electronic administrative services is 24/7/365 (24 hours a day, 7 days a week, 365 days a year) [3].

In some countries, this classic model of e-Governance is complemented by other e-Governance subjects and the relevant government links with them.

For example, in Great Britain, such an entity as "civil servants" is additionally singled out and the corresponding interaction of Government to Civil Servants (G2E – "government to employers") authorities in other countries is added to the e-Governance model in other countries. "International organizations and other states" (G2I – "government to international organizations"), which emphasizes the importance and features of government interaction with these subjects in e-governance [4].

In terms of the e-interaction content between e-Governance subjects, there are three main models of e-Governance: the continental European, the Anglo-American and the Asian models.

The continental European model is characterized by:

- the supranational structures existence (the European Parliament, the European Commission, the European Court of Justice), whose recommendations are binding on all the EU countries;
- high degree of European countries and peoples integration;
- clear legislation governing information relations in the European information space.

Management and activities of authorities and supranational structures in this model are aimed primarily at the citizens' needs – information systems and networks users (access to public information, prompt receipt of quality services, participation in public policy formation) [2].

The Anglo-American model (the USA, Canada, Great Britain).

In the USA, the main emphasis is made on the openness, transparency and accountability of government to citizens. This is reflected in the recent international initiatives of the US Government, namely in the "Partnership" [8].

In Great Britain the emphasis is made on:

- expanding the range of services provided by the government to citizens and business entities;

- increasing the government authorities efficiency;
- creating technical and educational conditions for full coverage of citizens with administrative services [8].

At the same time, one of the main purposes is to free civil servants from routine procedures of interaction with the population.

The Asian model of e-Governance takes into account the peculiarities of a specific management style, the Asian type of corporate culture and the public administration multilevel system. In this model, the main efforts are aimed at introducing modern information and communication technologies in the field of education and culture [8].

E-Governance is developing rapidly in Ukraine. Particularly recently, the work on creating the system of electronic interaction with the active participation of State Agency for e-Government in Ukraine has intensified. Today introducing the electronic interaction in the context of the rapid development of e-Governance is an extremely important issue.

In fact, many countries (Austria, Belgium, Ireland, Singapore, Thailand, Finland, Estonia, Denmark, Luxembourg, France, Germany, Spain, Italy etc.) are already living in the new dimensions of the digital society and economy, having introduced e-governance, having created government portals, having launched electronic digital signatures, ID- and MobileID-cards, having established interaction between public authorities, and most importantly – between a state and a citizen.

Large EU member states insist on introducing the single digital tax register and relevant databases for the digital economy. These plans essence is that companies pay taxes exactly where they work and earn, and not where they are registered. This is an opportunity to earn more from the digital economy. In this regard, the European Parliament is already calling for creating a single regulatory body for the EU to deal with regulation.

The most important event in the electronic interaction development in Estonia was the X-Road programme, a system that manages requests between unconnected computer environments. In one word, X-Road is an integrated data exchange system. Thanks to it, almost all administrative public services are provided in Estonia online and this significantly saves public funds and time [6].

In the USA where ideas for e-Governance development first emerged at the national level in 1998, which led to the opening of firstgov.gov portal (nowadays – usa.gov). To date this system covers almost 80% of all institutions.

In the post-Soviet countries, various projects are currently being implemented, which form the "e-Governance" basis: the telecommunications infrastructure is being improved, the widespread use of corporate systems in the customs, financial, and tax areas is beginning; various electronic registers and cadastres are being formed.

Ukraine actually joined this process in 2002, when the central part of the single web portal of the Cabinet

of Ministers was launched. At the beginning of April 2003, the "Electronic Ukraine" programme for 2003-2010 was developed in general, however, to date, no concrete actions under the programme have been completed.

Chile's experience reflects the process complexity of implementing e-governance as a public administration system. Currently, Chile is a country that, according to the UN report, occupies one of the leading positions in the ranking in its region for e-Governance and e-participation. Ukraine can adopt Chile's achievements in the startups development as a key idea for the innovative projects implementation that can strengthen the country's economy [2].

European countries have long been directly involved in providing public services online, successfully cooperating, involving and coordinating their citizens to participate in policy decisions adoption and implementation. The Belgian federal government is implementing service-oriented services, as Belgians want to create a single public space and integrate electronic services to meet their daily needs. E-Governance is recognized as an effective apparatus for broader public sector reforms.

Belgium's peculiarity is that it is multinational and multiethnic. The country itself is divided into two groups: the Flemings, who inhabit the north and centres, and the Walloons, who live in the southern provinces. The rapid development of e-governance in Belgium began with the creating in 2001 the Federal Department of ICT (Fedict), which replaced the Federal Office of ICT. The Belgian government is increasingly using digital technologies to provide modern electronic and mobile services aimed at providing benefits and convenience to all its citizens. There is an increase in the providing such services in all sectors, although to various degrees [6].

The main trend is the growth of mobile technologies and applications. This entails new opportunities for development and stimulates initiatives for new ways of providing services. Thus, e-Governance in Belgium as a model of successful implementing the information technologies in management is a useful experience for Ukraine, because such an approach helps to improve the services quality provided to citizens, speed up and simplify the process of providing them, integrate society into a single information space.

Table 1 offers a systematization of information, provides the main characteristics of each model, as well as the advantages and disadvantages of each.

The complexity of implementing the state e-Governance policy is largely due to the lack of Strategy and Programme in Ukraine for the information society development in general and e-Governance in particular. Today, introducing e-Governance is only partially regulated by several laws of Ukraine, two presidential decrees, 12 government regulations, which are insufficiently interconnected and somewhat contradictory [7].

Table 1. The Characteristics of the Most Common World Models of E-Governance in Comparison with Ukraine

№	E-Governance models	Characteristic features	Advantages/disadvantages
1	The continental European model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — supranational structures availability (European Parliament, European Commission, European Court of Justice), the recommendations of which are binding on all EU countries; — high degree of European countries and peoples integration; — clear legislation governing information relations in the European information space 	Is the most balanced, because it has to take into account the significant differences in the economic, political, cultural and technical potential of the EU members
2	The Anglo-American model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — expanding the range of services provided by the government to citizens and business entities; — increasing the government authorities efficiency; — creating technical and educational conditions for full coverage of citizens with administrative services. 	In the USA, the main emphasis is made on the openness, transparency and accountability of government to citizens. This is reflected in the recent international initiatives of the US Government, namely in the "Partnership"
3	The Asian model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — taking into account the features of a specific management style. Asian type of corporate culture and of public administration multilevel system. 	In this model, the main efforts are aimed at introducing modern information and communication technologies in the field of education and culture.
4	The Ukrainian model	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — rapid development since 2002, "Electronic Ukraine" programmes development, implementation of harmonized with the EU legal documents to the creation of standard projects "E-Ministry", "E-region" 	Departmental approach to their creation, significant duplication of information, lack of common standards and resources incompatibility, difficulty of access

Source: authors' own development

Some of them relate to traditional acts that are developed annually. First of all, this group includes, the Tasks for National Informatization Programme for three years and the Informatization Programme for a year, the annual report on the informatization status of Ukraine submitted by the Government to the Parliament, which have significantly lost their significance. These documents provide a set of measures aimed at implementing e-Governance, from the development and implementation of harmonized with the EU regulations to the creation of standard projects "E-Ministry", "E-Region".

According to this documentation, all executive bodies had to switch to electronic document management using an electronic digital signature by the end of 2009 and start providing interactive administrative services. The second group includes special documents that should be developed in order to increase the level of political and managerial objectification decisions on the information society development and introducing the e-Governance [1].

Conclusions

Introducing e-Governance and in particular e-interaction in Ukraine will not only make life easier for citizens to use their time, but also reduce corruption, through openness, objectivity and transparency of processes, eliminate bureaucratization, which constantly tires Ukrainians with its paperwork, queues, too complicated procedure and access.

In addition, it should be noted that it contributes to the environment preservation, some due to the lack of need to use paper. Using various technologies and implements for e-Governance contributes to civil servants' the of the work process transformation into a more mobile, efficient and comfortable.

E-Governance and e-identification are the perfect way to feel like a free citizen in your country and solve all issues with the help of gadgets, regardless of location and residence time.

Abstract

Rapid development of the information society in Ukraine it is generated by the processes of modernization of public administration, civil service, e-Governance introduction, increase number of management decisions. These decisions are accompanied by various forms of providing information. Using information and communication technologies expands the public authorities ability to promptly communicate their decisions to the general population, receive quality feedback from citizens, and citizens have the opportunity to participate in the political process, in particular by raising their awareness of current issues, activities public authorities and local governments, as well as to offer alternative ways to solve certain issues, to receive quality services. The current status of the regulatory framework in the field of e-Governance implementation and development indicates the diversity of norms, the presence of duplicate provisions and lack of an effective practical

implementation mechanism. E-Governance consists of three important elements of interaction: a state and a citizen interaction, a state and business interaction, a government interaction. E-Governance is one of the implements for the information society development, the implementation of which will help create conditions for open and transparent public administration.

Thus, e-Governance is the latest interactive system of public administration based on the principles of openness, transparency and accountability and which with the help of information and communication technologies ensures effective interaction of citizens, non-governmental organizations with public authorities. Introducing e-Governance and in particular e-interaction in Ukraine will not only make life easier for citizens to use their time, but also reduce corruption, through openness, objectivity and transparency of processes, eliminate bureaucratization, which constantly tires Ukrainians with its paperwork, queues, too complicated procedure and access. The article analyzes the main approaches to the definition of "e-Governance" and "e-democracy", starting from the approach where these concepts are considered only as convenient technologies of the information society, to the approach in which they are considered as the latest form of public administration, large-scale transformation of society, for the transition to an information society or knowledge society focused on meeting the citizens' needs.

Список літератури:

1. Е-урядування – ключ до реформ в Україні / Урядовий портал. – 2019. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://www.kmu.gov.ua/news/e-uryaduvannya-klyuch-do-reform-v-ukrayini>.
2. Зарубіжний досвід упровадження електронного урядування / авт. кол.: Т. Камінська, А. Камінський, М. Пасічник та ін.; за заг. ред. д-ра наук з держ. упр., проф. С. А. Чукот. – К., 2008. – 200 с. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://ktpu.kpi.ua/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/Zarubizhnij-dosvid-uprovadzhennya-elektronnoho-uryaduvannya.pdf>.
3. Барегамян С.Х., Карпі Ю.В. Електронне урядування на загальнодержавному, регіональному та місцевому рівнях: сучасний стан та перспективи впровадження в Україні. // Державне управління: удосконалення та розвиток – 2019. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: http://www.dy.nayka.com.ua/pdf/11_20_19/32.pdf.
4. Електронне урядування та електронна демократія: навч. посіб. у 15 ч., частина 6: Моніторинг, оцінювання та прогнозування розвитку системи електронного урядування / [С.К. Полумієнко]. – Київ: ФОП Москаленко О.М. – 2017. – 64 с.
5. Чукот С.А. Смарт-сіті чи електронне місто: сучасні підходи до розуміння впровадження е-урядування на місцевому рівні. Інвестиції: практика та досвід. – 2016. – № 13. – С. 89-93.
6. Електронний уряд: науково-практичний довідник / Укладачі: Чукот С.А., Клименко І.В., Линьов К.О. – 2016. – 85 с.
7. Про доступ до публічної інформації: Закон України від 13.01.2011 р. № 2939-VI. Відомості Верховної Ради України. – 2011. – № 32. – Ст. 314. [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2939-17>.
8. Григорян О.О. Світовий і вітчизняний досвід забезпечення прозорості та відкритості органів державної влади в реалізації публічної політики (інформаційний аспект). [Електронний ресурс] – Режим доступу: <http://academy.gov.ua/ej/ej15/txts/12GOOPIA.pdf>.

References:

1. Government portal. Official website. (2019). E-government – the key to reform in Ukraine. www.kmu.gov.ua. Retrieved from <https://www.kmu.gov.ua/news/e-uryaduvannya-klyuch-do-reform-v-ukrayini> [in Ukrainian].
2. T. Kaminska, A. Kaminsky, M. Pasichnyk and others. (2008). Foreign experience in implementing e-government. Chukut S.A. (Ed.). Retrieved from <https://ktpu.kpi.ua/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/Zarubizhnij-dosvid-uprovadzhennya-elektronnoho-uryaduvannya.pdf> [in Ukrainian].
3. Baramian S., Karpi Yu. (2019). Electronic governance at the state, regional and local levels: the current state and the prospects of implementation in Ukraine. *Derzhavne upravlinnya: udoskonalennya ta rozvytok*. Retrieved from http://www.dy.nayka.com.ua/pdf/11_20_19/32.pdf [in Ukrainian].
4. Polumienko S.K. (2017). E-government and e-democracy. Part 6: Monitoring, evaluation and forecasting of e-government system development. Kyiv: FOP Moskalenko O.M. [in Ukrainian].
5. Chukut, S.A. (2016). Smart City or E-City: Modern Approaches to Understanding E-Government Implementation at the Local Level. *Investment: practice and experience*, 13, 89-93.
6. Chukut, S.A. Klymenko, I.V. Lynov, K.O. (2016). *Elektronnyi uriad: nauково-praktychnyi dovidnyk [E-Government: A Scientific and Practical Handbook]* [in Ukrainian].
7. The Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine (2011). The Law of Ukraine "On Access to Public Information", Retrieved from <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2939-17> (Accessed 28 October 2019).

8. Hryhorian, O.O. (2012). World and domestic experience in ensuring the transparency and openness of public authorities in the implementation of public policy (information aspect). Retrieved from <http://academy.gov.ua/ej/ej15/txts/12GOOPIA.pdf> (Accessed 30 October 2019).

Посилання на статтю:

Sviridova S.S. Introducing E-Governance both in Ukraine and in the World / S. S. Sviridova, A. O. Bondarenko // Економіка: реалії часу. Науковий журнал. – 2020. – № 6 (52). – С. 70-75. – Режим доступу до журн.: <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2020/No6/70.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.06.2020.8. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4564580.

Reference a Journal Article:

Sviridova S.S. Introducing E-Governance both in Ukraine and in the World / S. S. Sviridova, A. O. Bondarenko // Economics: time realities. Scientific journal. – 2020. – № 6 (52).– P. 70-75. – Retrieved from <https://economics.opu.ua/files/archive/2020/No6/70.pdf>. DOI: 10.15276/ETR.06.2020.8. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4564580.

